

AGE HARDENING BEHAVIOR OF SiC WHISKER
REINFORCED 6061 ALUMINUM

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ABSTRACT

The age hardening behavior of silicon carbide whisker reinforced 6061 aluminum is presented and contrasted to that of undeformed and thermomechanically treated ingot 6061 aluminum. Times to achieve maximum hardness are shown to be a function of both aging temperature and material. Maximum hardness in undeformed 6061 is associated with precipitation of an intermediate β' phase, thermomechanically treated 6061 with β' and a needle-shaped transition phase precipitation and silicon carbide whisker reinforced 6061 with fine (<10 nm) zone formation. It is proposed that these differences must be considered when developing a generalized model for the deformation behavior of discontinuously reinforced metal matrix composites.

INTRODUCTION

Several recent investigations have examined the enhancements in mechanical properties that can be achieved through the incorporation of a discontinuous ceramic reinforcement, for example silicon carbide particulates or whiskers, into an appropriate aluminum alloy matrix [1-6]. These studies have shown that fabrication of such discontinuously reinforced composites can result in a 50-100 percent improvement in Young's modulus, yield strength and ultimate tensile strength over that which might be obtainable from age hardenable unreinforced ingot aluminum alloys.

Various models [7-9] have been proposed to explain these property enhancements. Each of these has had, by necessity, to consider the deformation behavior of the matrix itself. Most have considered that the

composite matrix is microstructurally and mechanically equivalent to that produced by selective thermomechanical treatment of the unreinforced alloy. Other studies of aluminum matrix composite precipitation kinetics [10,11] have also suggested that the development of the composite matrix microstructure is analogous to that reported for thermomechanically treated unreinforced aluminum. Precipitation has been reported to be enhanced by the presence of the ceramic reinforcement, with temperatures and times for achieving maximum hardness being decreased. The latter authors proposed that this change was due to increased precipitation of, for example the β' phase in 6061 aluminum. This increase was in turn ascribed to the high dislocation density in the aluminum matrix, this increased dislocation density having resulted from plastic relaxation of thermally induced SiC/aluminum interfacial stresses.

The present investigation was designed to examine the assumptions regarding the matrix precipitation behavior in discontinuously reinforced aluminum by comparing the age hardening of ingot 6061 aluminum, processed utilizing standard practices and selected thermomechanical treatments, and SiC whisker reinforced 6061.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

The chemical compositions of the 6061 ingot and composite materials examined in this investigation are given in Table 1. Details of the ingot processing procedures, as well as results of an extensive investigation on the influence of prior strain upon the precipitation kinetics of thermomechanically treated ingot 6061, have been reported previously by the author [12,13]. The aging results reported herein for deformed + aged ingot 6061 represent results obtained after rolling to a total reduction of 50 percent at 25 C, following solution treatment. The 6061 - 20 volume percent F-9 SiC whisker composite investigated in the present study was prepared by ARCO Metals utilizing standard blending and vacuum hot pressing procedures as practiced during 1984. This involved wet blending of prealloyed, inert gas atomized, 6061 powder, drying and vacuum hot pressing above the alloy solidus. Following hot pressing the whisker reinforced 6061 billet was homogenized and extruded to a 12.5 mm thick by 127 mm wide (nominal) plate bar (extrusion ratio of 11.3:1).

TABLE 1
Chemical Composition of 6061 Ingot and Composite Matrix

	Mg	Si	Cu	Cr	Fe	Mn	Zn
Ingot	0.98	0.68	0.26	0.2	0.09	0.05	0.02
Composite	1.19	0.77	0.35	0.22	0.32	<0.01	0.02

The kinetics of aging for all materials examined in this investigation were monitored at selected intervals, following solution treatment at 525 C for 1 hr. and water quenching, by superficial hardness measurements. Hardness readings reported are the average of 5 measurements made on metallographically prepared surfaces, the examination plane always lying normal to either the rolling or extrusion direction. While the differing work hardening characteristics of the undeformed + aged ingot, the deformed + aged ingot and the SiC whisker reinforced composite precludes a direct comparison of the maximum hardness (strengths) obtainable in each system, the reported hardness measurements can be utilized to examine the kinetics or rates of precipitation reaction.

Transmission electron microscopy was the principal method for examining the dislocation/precipitate substructural interactions. Details of thin foil preparation for the ingot system has been reported elsewhere [13]. Preparation of the composite foils were similar except that final polishing involved argon ion thinning. Examination of the thin foils employed either a JEOL 100C or 200A.

RESULTS

A direct comparison of the artificial aging response at 125 and 175 C for ingot and SiC_w reinforced 6061 is shown in figures 1 and 2, respectively. These results suggest that there is a distinct difference in the age hardening behavior of ingot and whisker reinforced 6061. At 125 C, the hardness of undeformed 6061 initially decreases before increasing to a maximum value after aging for 256 hrs. The hardness of deformed + aged ingot 6061 exhibits a plateau upon initial aging, followed by an increase, with a hardness maxima after aging for 256 hrs at 125 C. The same hardness plateau is observed in SiC_w reinforced 6061. However in this instance the hardness plateau extends to longer aging

times (4 hrs versus 0.75 hrs). In addition, the hardness maxima observed in SiC_w reinforced 6061 aged at 125 C occurs at longer aging times (512 hrs versus 256 hrs).

These differences in age hardening response between undeformed 6061, deformed 6061 and SiC_w reinforced 6061 are even more distinct after artificial aging at 175 C. In general the hardness of undeformed 6061 increases with aging time at 175 going through a maxima after aging

Figure 1: Age hardening response for undeformed, deformed SiC_w reinforced 6061 aged at 125 C.

for 4 hrs. In contrast, the hardness of deformed 6061, following an initial plateau, gradually decreases with increasing aging time. Finally the hardness response of SiC_w reinforced 6061 aged at 175 C exhibits a gradual increase in hardness with aging time, with a maxima being observed after aging for 2 hrs.

Detailed transmission electron microscopy studies [12,13] have shown that artificial aging of undeformed 6061 proceeds in the sequence, supersaturated solid solution \rightarrow vacancy-silicon clusters \rightarrow GP zones \rightarrow coherent needle-shaped phase \rightarrow β' semicoherent transition phase \rightarrow

Figure 2: Age hardening response for undeformed, deformed and SiC_w reinforced 6061 aluminum aged at 175 C.

equilibrium β Mg_2Si , with maximum hardness being associated with formation of the β' phase.

These same investigations have shown that the precipitation sequence in deformed 6061 depends upon the artificial aging temperature. At low temperatures, where initial GP zone formation is an important factor in the precipitation sequence, i.e., below the GP solvus, prior deformation does not effect the precipitation sequence and maximum strength is again associated with formation of the β' phase. At higher temperatures, i.e., above the GP zone solvus, prior deformation tends to promote heterogeneous precipitation of the needle-shaped phase, with maximum hardness being associated with precipitation of the needle-shaped and β' phases.

Transmission electron microscope examination of SiC_w reinforced 6061 shows that the matrix contains a high dislocation density, figure 3. However, maximum hardness in the composite does not involve heterogeneous

needle-shaped or β' precipitation, rather it appears to be associated with precipitation of extremely fine (<10 nm) zones, figure 4.

Figure 3: Transmission electron micrograph illustrating high dislocation density observed in 6061 - 20 volume percent SiC_w reinforced aluminum.

DISCUSSION

The results of this investigation indicate that the hardening behavior of undeformed, deformed and SiC_w discontinuously reinforced 6061 aluminum are quite different. The effect of ceramic reinforcement on the aging kinetics of aluminum alloys depends upon aging temperature. For example, in SiC_w 6061, maximum hardness occurs at earlier aging times, when compared to undeformed 6061 if aging is carried out at 175 C, and at later times if aged at 125 C. Maximum hardness in undeformed + aged 6061 is associated with precipitation of a β' transition deformed + aged (thermomechanically treated) 6061 with precipitation of a fine needle-shaped phase in combination with the β' phase and SiC_w reinforced 6061 with precipitation of fine zones.

These results also show that modeling the behavior of aged aluminum metal matrix composites by simply considering the matrix to be equivalent to a deformed + aged ingot alloy is inappropriate, more complex formulations will be required. Rather, the composite matrix will have to

be considered to have a unique microstructure and flow behavior which is developed as a consequence of the interaction of reinforcement, dislocation substructure and thermal history.

Figure 4: Transmission electron micrograph of peak aged 6061 - 20 volume percent SiC_w reinforced aluminum.

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